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“ONLINE SELLING”

Angelica noticed her neighbors were staring at her as she was walking down the street. She has been mocked for selling “ukay-ukay” online. Her neighbors say she’s cheap. She used to be an accountant but she gave it all up in order to take care of her sick father. It was never an easy decision, but she believes, it was worth it. Her father needs her, after all, she is his only daughter. She doesn’t care what people will say about her as long as she’s working with dignity.

Angelica always has a scheduled live selling on Facebook, and TikTok. She even makes videos about clothes haul and reviews on YouTube. One day, while doing her Facebook live, someone named Nerissa commented “Mine” on one of her items. This means that Nerissa is willing to buy the item. Nerissa went from commenting to only one item, to commenting to a total of ten items.

To make sure of the legitimacy of the buyer, Angelica contacted her through messenger. After a series of conversations, they both agreed that Angelica will ship the items as soon as Nerissa sends her the money through GCash.

The following day, Angelica prepared to ship the items. Nerissa messaged her and promised to send the money at twelve noon because she is still on duty, she can’t leave before twelve noon. Angelica waited, it was already twelve noon, but still, Nerissa had not sent the money. So, Angelica decided to call her. Nerissa answered and apologized, saying she’s currently having the money wired in her GCash account. She asked Angelica if she could just ship the items before she sends the money since her own clients are also waiting for the items to be delivered. She explained, she’s also going to sell the items to her friends. Angelica gets a hint that something’s not right. Why would she ship the unpaid items? How can she be sure Nerissa’s not going to scam her. So, to make sure, she asked that she and Nerissa have a video call. Nerissa refused by cancelling all her calls. “That’s it.” Angelica said to herself, “This good old scammer thinks she can get me. But she’s wrong. I’d rather lose a profit than bite to this trap.”

Angelica decided to cancel her transactions with Nerissa. Nerissa got furious, saying she’s not a scammer. She even threatened Angelica that she’d lose a big amount of profit if she continues to cancel their transaction. She even added that she will convince her friends to boycott Angelica’s live selling events. But Angelica’s not afraid. One scammer will never bring her down. Even though there were many times that she encounters bogus buyers, still, she will never give up with this business. Although a lot of people treat online selling as a joke, she has proven this as an effective way of living. For now, her business may seem unstable, but she doesn’t want to give up. Someday, all her hard work will pay off. For now, she just needs to be patient, understanding, and most of all clever.

